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Transport of selected organophosphorus pesticides through alluvial sediment with the addition of microbially inoculated chars

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The aim of this study

- ✓ was to investigate the transport behavior of two selected organophosphorus pesticides (chlorpyrifos-CP and chlorpyrifos-methyl-CPM) through Danube alluvial sediment in the absence and in the presence of microbially inoculated chars originated from sugar beet shreds (biochar produced at 400°C and three hydrochars produced at 180, 200, and 220°C).

Chlorpyrifos

Chlorpyrifos-methyl

Materials and methods

Synthesis and inoculation of carbon-based materials

The production of **biochar** included the application of **slow pyrolysis** (model Naberthem S27 furnace) of the investigated biomass (sugar beet shreds) at a temperature of 400 °C.

Hydrochars originated from sugar beet shreds were synthesized at three different temperatures, 180 °C, 200 °C, and 220 °C, using a 3000 mL volume autoclave (Deutsch and Neumann, model 10253).

Bacillus megaterium BD5 was isolated from the Danube alluvial sediment and used for inoculation of biochar and hydrochars.

Characterization of investigated materials (Danube alluvial sediment and chars)

Multipoint BET (Brunauer–Emmett–Teller) SSA, average pore diameter, and pore volume of all materials were determined using N₂ adsorption-desorption analysis at 77 K with an analyzer for the characterization of porous and powdered materials (AutosorbTMIQ; Quantachrome Instruments). Particle size distribution was determined according to ISO 11277:2009.

Materials and methods

Column experiments

Sample analysis:

GC/MS

Data analysis:

advective-dispersive equation (ADE)

Results

Characterization of investigated materials

Adsorbent	SSA (m ² /g)	Micropore (cm ³ /g)		Mesopore (cm ³ /g)	Pore radius (Å)	Pore volume (cm ³ /g)
	BET	t-test	HK	BJH	Average	Total
Alluvial sediment	1.49	0	0	0	79.0	0.059
B_S	20.6	0.003	0.0086	0.016	25.5	0.0263
HTC_S 180	3.87	0	0.0011	0.023	119	0.0230
HTC_S 200	4.06	0	0.0012	0.025	126	0.0256
HTC_S 220	5.53	0	0.0016	0.027	100	0.0277

Results

Transport parameters for the selected organophosphorus pesticides obtained through a column filled with alluvial sediment without and in the presence of microbially inoculated chars

Column	Compounds	Water permeability V_w (m/h)	Retardation factor, R_d	Effective dispersivity, α_{eff}	Biodegradation, λ
Alluvial sediment	Thiourea	0.92	1	0.009	0
	CP	0.92	16	0.009	1.80
	CPM	0.92	15.5	0.009	4.15
B_S	Thiourea	0.980	1	0.03	0
	CP	0.980	275	0.2	4.5
	CPM	0.980	145	0.35	1.6
HTC_S 180	Thiourea	0.500	1	0.002	0
	CP	0.500	23	0.01	2.3
	CPM	0.500	20	0.2	1.2
HTC_S 200	Thiourea	0.600	1	0.02	0
	CP	0.600	40	0.06	1.8
	CPM	0.600	32	0.15	0.4
HTC_S 220	Thiourea	0.600	1	0.006	0
	CP	0.600	115	0.1	4.3
	CPM	0.600	25	0.15	1.4

Results

Breakthrough curves of investigated organic compounds through the alluvial sediment

Results

Breakthrough curves of investigated organic compounds in the presence of inoculated chars in alluvial sediment column

Conclusion

- The addition of inoculated carbon based materials in a column filled with alluvial sediment significantly increases the retardation coefficient (R_d). This may be a consequence of **simultaneous adsorption** on the organic matter of the alluvial sediment, on carbon-based materials and results of **biosorption**.
- **A higher retardation coefficient (R_d)** in column experiments with the addition of inoculated chars was observed for **biochar** than for hydrochars, which is directly correlated with the **higher specific surface area (SSA)** of the investigated biochar.
- Generally, the **addition of inoculated carbon-based materials** to contaminated sediments has the **potential as a remediation technique** to inhibit the leaching of pollutants to groundwaters and affect their immobilization.

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Thank you!

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